

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS ADIDAS SHOES WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY**Dr. T. Vasumathi,**Professor, Department of Commerce with International Business,
Dr. N.G.P Arts and Science College, Coimbatore-48.**S. Rajavel,**Student, B. Com (IB), Department of Commerce with International Business,
Dr. N.G.P Arts and Science College, Coimbatore-48.**ABSTRACT:**

The study titled “A Study on Consumer Perception towards Adidas Shoes with Reference to Coimbatore City” examines how consumers perceive Adidas footwear and the factors influencing their purchase decisions, satisfaction, and brand loyalty. The research is based on a descriptive research design, and primary data were collected from 100 respondents in Coimbatore city using a structured questionnaire. The data were analyzed using statistical tools such as percentage analysis, mean score analysis, and ranking analysis.

The findings reveal that comfort, brand image, quality, and durability are the main factors influencing consumer perception, with comfort ranking as the most important. The study also shows that social media is the major source of awareness, and most consumers express high satisfaction and willingness to recommend Adidas shoes. However, the price of Adidas shoes is perceived as relatively high by some consumers. Overall, the study highlights the importance of maintaining product quality, comfort, and effective marketing strategies to strengthen consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty.

Keywords:

Adidas Shoes, Consumer Perception, Customer Satisfaction, Brand Image, Comfort, Brand Loyalty, Purchase Decision, Footwear Market, Social Media Awareness, Coimbatore City.

INTRODUCTION OF THE STUDY

Consumer perception plays a crucial role in determining the success of a brand in today’s highly competitive market. In the footwear industry, especially in the sports and lifestyle segment, consumers evaluate products based on several factors such as comfort, quality, durability, design, price, and brand reputation. Branded footwear has become more than just a necessity; it represents lifestyle, fashion, and personal identity. Among the many global sportswear brands, **Adidas** has established a strong reputation for its innovative designs, advanced technology, and high-quality products. The brand is widely preferred by athletes, fitness enthusiasts, and young consumers who seek both performance and style in their footwear.

In India, the demand for branded sports shoes has been steadily increasing due to rising health awareness, growing interest in sports and fitness activities, and changing lifestyle patterns. **Coimbatore city**, known for its educational institutions and youthful population, represents a significant market for branded footwear brands like Adidas. Consumers in this city are influenced by various factors such as advertising, social media, peer recommendations, and personal experience while making purchase decisions. Therefore, understanding consumer perception towards Adidas shoes is important for identifying satisfaction levels, brand loyalty, and areas for improvement. This study aims to analyse the perception of consumers towards Adidas shoes in Coimbatore city and to identify the factors that influence their buying behaviour and overall satisfaction.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The footwear industry is highly competitive with many brands offering similar products. Although Adidas is a well-known global sports footwear brand, changing consumer preferences, price sensitivity, and expectations regarding comfort, quality, and design create challenges in maintaining customer satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, it is important to understand how consumers perceive Adidas shoes and the factors influencing their purchase decisions. This study aims to analyse consumer perception towards Adidas shoes in Coimbatore city.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study focuses on consumer perception towards Adidas shoes in Coimbatore city. It examines factors such as comfort, quality, durability, price, design, and brand image that influence consumer buying behavior. The study also helps understand customer satisfaction and brand loyalty among Adidas shoe users.

OBJECTIVES:

- To analyze the demographic and socio-economic profile of Adidas footwear consumers in Coimbatore city.
- To examine the level of consumer awareness and brand familiarity regarding Adidas footwear.
- To assess customer satisfaction and its impact on brand loyalty and recommendation behavior.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Research Design:** Descriptive Research
- **Area of the Study:** Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu
- **Sampling Size:** 100 respondents
- **Sampling Method:** Simple Random Sampling.
- **Sources of Data:** Primary data and secondary data
- **Data Analysis Tools:** Simple percentage analysis, Ranking analysis.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

- Kotler (2018) emphasized that consumer perception plays a crucial role in shaping brand positioning, as it influences how consumers evaluate product value and develop long-term loyalty in competitive markets. Similarly, Singh and Verma (2020) found that factors such as comfort, durability, and brand image are the key determinants of customer satisfaction in branded sports shoes, which in turn leads to repeat purchase behavior among consumers. These studies highlight that positive consumer perception and satisfaction are essential for building strong brand loyalty in the footwear industry. Therefore, understanding consumer perception helps companies improve their marketing strategies and product offerings.
- Keller (2018) stated that brand equity is developed through consistent and positive consumer experiences with a brand. According to the study, when consumers perceive a brand as reliable and high in quality, it strengthens their trust and increases their intention to purchase the product. In the footwear industry, strong brand equity helps companies maintain a competitive advantage and build long-term customer relationships. This shows that maintaining a positive brand image and customer experience is important for sustaining consumer loyalty.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**1 Age-wise Distribution of Respondents**

<u>Age Group</u>	<u>No. of Respondents</u>	<u>Percentage (%)</u>
<u>Below 18</u>	<u>8</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>18-25</u>	<u>42</u>	<u>42</u>
<u>26-35</u>	<u>30</u>	<u>30</u>
<u>36-45</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>12</u>
<u>Above 45</u>	<u>8</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>Total</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>100</u>

INTERPRETATION:

The majority of respondents (42%) belong to the 18–25 age group, indicating that Adidas shoes are more popular among young consumer

Mean Score and Ranking of Consumer Perception Factors

Factors	Mean Score	Rank
Comfort	4.5	1
Brand Image	4.4	2
Quality	4.3	3
Durability	4.2	4
Price	3.6	5

INTERPRETATION:

The mean score analysis reveals that comfort ranks first with the highest mean score, indicating that consumers highly value comfort while purchasing Adidas shoes. Brand image and quality also receive high mean scores, reflecting Adidas's strong market reputation and product standards. Price ranks last, suggesting that consumers perceive Adidas shoes as relatively expensive. Overall, functional benefits and brand strength play a major role in shaping consumer perception satisfaction.

FINDINGS

1. He Majority Of Respondents Belong To The 18 To25 Age Group, Indicating That Adidas Shoes Are More Popular Among Young Consumers.
2. Comfort, Brand Image, Quality, And Durability Are The Major Factors Influencing Consumer Perception, With Comfort Ranked As The Most Important Factor.
3. Most Respondents Show A High Level Of Satisfaction And Willingness To Recommend Adidas Shoes, Indicating Strong Customer Loyalty Toward The Brand.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Adidas should introduce **more affordable pricing options or promotional offers** to attract price-sensitive consumers.
2. The company should **introduce new designs and a wider variety of models** to attract fashion-conscious and young consumers.
3. should **strengthen its social media marketing and digital promotions** to increase brand awareness and influence purchase decisions.

CONCLUSION:

The study on consumer perception towards Adidas shoes in Coimbatore city reveals that the brand has a strong and positive image among consumers, especially among the younger age group. Factors such as comfort, quality, durability, and brand image play a significant role in influencing consumer purchase decisions. Among these factors, comfort is identified as the most important aspect considered by consumers while buying Adidas shoes. The study also shows that social media plays a major role in creating awareness about the brand. Overall, consumers show a high level of satisfaction and willingness to recommend Adidas shoes to others. However, the price of Adidas shoes is perceived as relatively high by some consumers. Therefore, by focusing on competitive pricing, innovative designs, and effective marketing strategies, Adidas can further strengthen customer satisfaction and brand loyalty in the market.

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